

So thinking the king returned, and at once ordered the minister to be released and to be brought before him. He came and stood before his lord accordingly, and the king explained to him all about the lion and how his words had proved to be true so far. "But how can my sending you to jail be for the best?" said the king.

Replied the minister, "My most noble lord! Had it not been for my imprisonment in the

jail I would have accompanied you to the forest and fallen a prey to the lion. After rejecting you for being deformed he would have taken me away for his feast. So I should have died. Therefore even my having lived in the jail for a day was for the best."

The king was extremely pleased with the reply and received his minister into still greater confidence.

MISCELLANEA.

RAMBLES AMONG RUINS IN CENTRAL INDIA.

Thirty or forty miles north of the river Narmadâ, in Central India, there lies a tract, enclosed east and west by the rivers Bînâ and Pârbatî and south by the Vindhyan scarp, in which there are many remarkable Buddhist, Jain, and Brâhmanical ruins. They consist of topes, temples, tanks, monasteries, and columns. This district was formerly part of Gôṇḍwâna. A low range of rocky hills divides it from the Serôñj plateau on the north.

Through its very centre, towards the north, flows the sacred river Bêtwâ, rising among the upland valleys of the range. Its upper course is tortuous; and the rocky hills round which it sweeps, with the broad vales and narrow glens over which the holy stream gently glides or through which it swiftly rushes, were for many hundred years before and subsequent to the commencement of the Christian era a great centre of religion and of wealth. Dotted over mountain and plain the ruins of remarkable works of art and utility testify even now to the religious zeal and mercantile activity of the past.

The oldest and most famed of these is the Buddhist tope upon the Sâñchi Hill, overlooking the Bêtwâ. Probably it formed the earliest centre of attraction, which for so long drew crowds of devotees and also a multitude of all classes to a district which, if it was as wild then as now, must have been singularly uninviting for human settlement. It is not my purpose in this paper to attempt a description of this famous fane, or of those of a like nature which cluster around it, or indeed to give any detailed archaeological description; but simply to sketch what I have seen of the lesser known remains of towns, temples, and tanks, still lying for the most part in the jungle and out of the beaten track of travellers, but which are about to be rendered accessible by the Indian Midland Railway.

At a very early period of this settlement, perhaps a few centuries before our era, the city of Bês-nagar must have been founded. Its site was about two miles from the Sâñchi hill. Greek and Buddhist coins, ploughed up every rains, testify to its antiquity. Moreover, its remarkable position and selected means of defence, stamp it to have been contemporary with the ancient cities of Êran, Dhâr, and Sîhôr, similarly situated and defended. It was placed between the rivers Bês and Bêtwâ, above their point of junction, within a triangle formed by a curve of the latter river and completed by an artificial communication between the two rivers. The earth excavated was formed into a high rampart, topped with brick; and thus, surrounded by deep rivers and high banks, good defence and an ample supply of pure water were assured. This circumscribed area of not more than two square miles must have been subsequently much extended. There are ruins across both the Bêtwâ and the Bês, extending to the modern Bhêlsâ on the east, to the Udigiri hills on the west, and to the spot where General Sir A. Cunningham dug up the *kalpa-druma* and the statue of Mâyâdêvi on the north. A great, rich and populous city must have stood here for centuries, perchance for a thousand years,—a focus of civilization and a centre of wealth.

The sculptured *kalpa-druma* (wishing-tree) and the statue of Mâyâdêvi (the mother of Buddha), which adorned columns in this city, are now in the Calcutta Museum. But the interesting sculptured ancient caves of the Udigiri hill, still untouched by the hand of time, are full of interest. Scattered around are remnants of capitals and columns enough to enrich a museum, and buried beneath mounds probably lie interesting, and perhaps invaluable, stone records of the ruined city and temples.

From the above account it will be understood that Bês-nagar was built between two rivers. But the sister city of Êran, fifty miles to the north-east,

in the Sâgar District, was efficiently defended by a single loop of one river, the Binâ, and an artificial trench and rampart, while their contemporary, Dhâr, in south-western Mâlwa, was on an island surrounded by a ring of lakes, each connected with the other by deep ditches covered by lofty ramparts, which still tower forty or fifty feet above the plain. Sihôr was defended on a smaller scale, but in a like manner to Bêsnagar. The Midland Railway runs between Sâñchi and Bêsnagar, with the great tope on its right and the Udigiri hill on its left; and after crossing the Bêtwâ it passes close by the ruined city to the Bhêlsâ Station.

Twenty miles east of Bhêlsâ, around the modern town of Gyârispur, lie some most beautiful ruined temples. One, indeed, affords a sublime sight, owing to its noble proportions, and the grandeur of its site and surroundings. I allude to the magnificent shrine on the extreme point to the east of the hill behind the city. Its site and platform beautifully sculptured were boldly carved out of the hill crest. On the spot, a temple of noble proportions and exquisite detail was erected, in such a manner that it appears to be a part of the cliff under which it nestles, perched 500 feet above the plain. There are few more impressive spots, and the view from the temple platform over fertile fields of green wheat, in the cold weather, is one not easily forgotten. I remember this temple, though with a damaged exterior, yet with its interior shrine intact. Treasure-seekers have now wrecked the statues and destroyed the floors, but even at the present time the view of the interior, when a flood of light enters through the eastern door from the rising sun, is very beautiful; at all other times it is dark, and can only be seen by the aid of torches. In no temple have I seen a more curious effect than that of the entry of the rays of the rising sun into the inner shrine of this one. To the ancient worshippers it must have been a supreme moment, when the Sun-god kissed into seeming life the beautiful goddess at the shrine.

At the base of the hill, not far from the high road between Bhêlsâ and Gyârispur, are two rare and interesting temples, the Bajranâth shrines, which will well reward close inspection; as also will the exquisitely carved roofless columns.

About thirty-four miles north of Bhêlsâ stands the rare and beautiful temple of Udayêsvara within the town of Udayapura. This is the only ancient fane in the neighbourhood, that escaped desecration or destruction at the hands of the Musalmân conquerors. Built not long before the invasion of Muḥammad Tughlaq, it was ordered to be blown up by him on his

conquest of the city. Bags of powder were heaped inside and under the tower; but, watered possibly by the power of priestly gold, the powder would not burn; and the emperor, in acknowledgment of the miracle, ordered the preservation of the temple, compromising with his conscience by turning one of the two Vêda reading-halls in front and rear of the building into a mosque, dividing it by a wall from the heathen structure, and recording the fact on the archways of the entrance. This has preserved the temple to the present day, alike from the iconoclast Aurangzêb as from the occasional outbursts of fanaticism of the Mându kings of Mâlwa. The temple is of perfect proportions and of noble form, covered with very fine sculptures. It is most strikingly harmonious, and is a perfect gem of art, not only as a whole, but in its several parts. The tapering spire, unusually lofty, is seen from afar, though, such are its perfect proportions, that its great height is not noticed when viewed near. There are three entrances, each covered by a grand porch, and the interior is even more strikingly perfect than the exterior; but, unfortunately, it is so dark that it can be only seen with the aid of torches, when it will be observed that at one time the Jains must have possessed themselves of the temple, though probably it was originally a Brâhmanical shrine. It is a curious fact that the oil for the temple lights is and has always been supplied by the family of Agra Bukera, who are Punwâr Râjpûts, and claim descent from Râja Bhôj, of Dhârâ, in whose reign, or by whose family perhaps, the temple was erected. This is interesting, though General Sir A. Cunningham has been unable to trace any probable descendants of that famous king.

Twenty miles further east are to be found, in and round about the modern Pathârî, most interesting and rare remains. The most striking is the famous stone column or *lât*, the largest and most massive in the district, though far less beautiful than the slender graceful monolith of Êran, twenty miles to the north. Around it are many interesting ruins fully described in the *Archæol. Survey of India*, Vol. VII. But the most beautiful and extensive is the ruined temple of Gadarmal, situated on the banks of a tank about a mile and a half from the present town in a picturesque position, near well-wooded but rugged hills, originally constructed after the manner of that of Udayêsvara. This temple was overturned and then was put together again unskillfully by the Jains with little order or symmetry. The exquisite *tôran* or gateway must have escaped, for, though half-ruined by neglect, it is still singularly beautiful, and is worth travelling far

to see. This unique gate, tottering to complete ruin, ought to be carried away to a place of safety, together with the finely sculptured and richly carved life-size *basso relievo* of the mother of Buddha and her infant. The temple is in Sindhiâ's dominions, and there would be no difficulty in obtaining permission for the removal of the gate. There are many Jain temples scattered about, some dating from the seventh century.

Twenty miles north-east are the remains of the Êran temples, so famed for their graceful columns and valuable inscriptions. On a high bank of the Binâ river, the beauty of the situation adds a charm to these beautiful and romantic ruins.

Returning towards Bhôpâl, twenty miles south of the city are the remains of the city of Bhôjpur, not far from which is situated the ruined or uncompleted temple of Bhôjpur, famed far and wide on account of its gigantic *linga*. This temple is remarkable on account of being probably the only one in India which, remaining unfinished, presents the earthen ramp up the easy slope of which were rolled, after the manner of the most ancient builders (as portrayed on Egyptian and Assyrian sculpture) the immense stone blocks for the walls and roofs. This fact, apart from its grand internal proportions, attaches great interest to this temple, which, though in a ruined condition, is still used for worship, and owing to its gigantic polished quartzite *linga*, has wide local fame. I do not think the inscription on the lintel of the door has ever been carefully copied and translated. The temple evidently was built some little time subsequently to the formation of the lake on the shore of which it stands, and most likely after the city of Bhôjpur had become a place of importance. The ruins of this large town stand close by. It seems to have fallen into decay in the fifteenth century, on the destruction of the dam and subsidence of the waters of the lake.

The great Bhôjpur lake, just alluded to, was without doubt the largest and most beautiful sheet of fresh water in India; indeed, the only one worthy of the name of lake as we understand it. It covered a valley which presents the most remarkable feature that, though it is so extensive, only two breaks occur in its wall of hills,—one a little more than one hundred, the other about five hundred yards wide. Both of them were spanned by very remarkable dams, consisting of an earthen central *band* faced on both sides, outer and inner, with immense blocks of stone laid one on the other without mortar, but fitting so truly as to be watertight, the two faces sloping inwards from the base. The lesser opening was

closed by a *band* 87 feet in height, and 300 feet thick at the base, or even more; the greater, by one in places 40 feet high, and about 100 feet broad on the top; and, though the first-mentioned *band* is now a complete wreck, the latter is intact and still continues to turn the river Kâliasôt into the Bêtawâ, and from its top the old bed of the stream is recognisable. The lesser but higher *band* was broken by Shâh Hussain, the greatest of the Mându kings, for the purpose of utilizing the bed of the lake; and, though tradition relates that he never personally benefited by this act, the fact of the present fertility of the valley, still growing the best wheat in the country, proves his practical statesmanship, however much we may regret the loss of a water storage of such rare size and beauty for India. The Gônâs who live in the thick jungle still surrounding this valley, tell us that it took an army of labourers three months to destroy the dam, while three years elapsed before the lake was emptied, and thirty before its bed was fit for human habitation.

I do not know that the story of the construction of this lake by Râja Bhôj of Dhârâ has ever been written. It is an interesting tradition. It runs that Râja Bhôj was stricken with a severe illness, some say leprosy, which the court physicians failed to remedy. He therefore had recourse to a holy recluse, who lived at a distance, but was widely famed for his miraculous cures. The monk, after considering the case and performing many incantations and examinations of signs and omens, gave the following oracular decree:—that the king would die of the disease, unless he was able to construct a lake so great as to be the largest in India and fed by 365 streams, or a stream for every day in the year. By bathing in such a lake, on a certain day, at a certain hour, he would be cleansed, not otherwise. The king, it is related, gathered together men learned in all the sciences, and settled in his capital by reason of his liberal patronage, and consulted them. They recommended that skilled engineers should be sent along the valleys east and west of the Vindhyan range, which lie near Dhâr, to explore the country and report upon the feasibility of such a lake being constructed. And it is said that, after a long and weary investigation and many hopeless failures and immense expenditure, they discovered the valley, subsequently enclosed, in which there happened to be the head-waters of the holy river Bêtawâ. But, alas! only 359 springs and streams fed the waters flowing through the valley. The difficulty was however, eventually overcome by Kâlia, a Gônâ chief, pointing out the missing river, which with its tributaries, made up the number, and was

The bed of the Ancient Lake of king Bhoja near Bhopal.

accordingly named, to this day, Kâlia's river, or the Kâliasôt.

This tradition preserves two important facts, *viz.*:—(1) That the drainage area of the sources of the Bêtwâ was insufficient to fill the valley through which it flowed and which it was intended to enclose. (2) That the lake thus formed was of unusual size for an Indian lake. A study of the local topography and the remains of the works, clearly proves that the engineers of those days undoubtedly understood that the drainage area of the Bêtwâ and its tributaries was insufficient for their purpose, and that they skilfully supplied the deficiency by turning into the Bêtwâ valley the waters of another river, which, rising twenty miles to the west, and flowing naturally outside the hill-enclosed valley, would increase the drainage area by at least five hundred square miles. This was accomplished by the creation of the magnificent cyclopean dam on which stands the old fort of Bhôpâl, and which, previous to the Bhôpâl dynasty, was covered with finely sculptured Jain temples. From the storage lake thus obtained, a river flowed at right angles to its former course round the hills into the Bêtwâ valley, and became a most valuable feeder to the constructors of the great lake, because it carried the surplus waters of the storage lake into the larger lake for three full months after the close of the rains. This river is the Kâliasôt.

To test the tradition as to the lake's unusual size, emphasised by the local saying, *tâl hô tô Bhôpâl tâl, sab dâsre talyâ*—"if there be a lake it is Bhôpâl lake; all others are ponds,"—a line of levels was run from the waste weir or ancient outfall to the Bhôpâl railway levels, and thence other lines were projected. These, when plotted on sheets 16, 17 and 26 of the Bhôpâl-Mâlwa Topographical Survey Maps, proved that the ancient lake covered the valley to the extent of two hundred and fifty square miles,—its bed lying as shewn in the accompanying map,—and must have formed the largest, as it did the most beautiful, lake in the peninsula of India, giving one unbroken sheet of water save where islands added to its beauty. It was in places a hundred feet deep; and on all sides it was surrounded by high hills covered with verdure to the water's edge, except at the clearings, around the towns that soon sprung up on its shores. A ramble among these discovers that the wavelets of five hundred years have left their marks; and one is struck by the many inlets and picturesque outer valleys, which, when filled with water, must have appeared almost like separate lakelets and must have been of weird beauty.

The waste weir, discovered by the writer in one of these rambles, lies buried in almost impenetrable jungle, and is certainly worth a visit. It is a cutting through the solid rock of one of the lower hills on the east side. It is at the blunt apex of a triangular valley, opening from near the great dam, and is probably two miles from it in a direct line. Its position, so far from the dam, affords another proof of the practical ability of the Hindu engineers of the time; for any error in levels would have quickly destroyed the dam, which, though stone-faced on both sides, was filled in by earth, and could not long have withstood an overflow. There are signs on its rocky and unbroken sides which show that high-water mark was within six feet of the top.

The second and lower but longer *band* already mentioned was thrown across the only other opening of this remarkable valley, and by its construction the Kâliasôt was turned off from its course at right angles into the Bêtwâ. It is so covered with jungle that it escaped even the keen eyes of the Topographical Survey Officers. It is constructed in like manner to the other one, but is still unbroken. Its top is used as part of the high road from Bhôpâl to Kâliakhêri.

On the ancient shore at Bhôjpur the Gônds point out more than one group of large flat stones,—two upright and one horizontal,—like Keltic remains, and revered because they were used by Râja Bhôj as his boat-houses. Sitting on one of these, and gazing afar over a perfectly flat valley bounded by the hills forming the western shore, it is not difficult to fancy an actual sea taking the place of the sea of waving green wheat, or to hear, in the rattling of the *pippal* leaves overhead, the lapping of the wavelets under the morning breeze on the rocks below. It is most interesting to listen to the Gônds telling their old-world tales of the ancient sea; how Râja Bhôj, whose name and memory seems beloved beyond all others in Central India, used to sail over to the opposite shore every morning for his early orisons among the Buddhist caves,—perhaps then still a monastery on the top of Bhimbêtil hill,—and then returning for his noon-day meal. They tell of the traditions of the lake-cities now in ruins, of the spirits of the deep that interfered with the completion of the great temple, and many other tales of old connected with the mighty fort of Gonar, away on the mountains beyond the western shore. They relate with awe how the fort's deep dyke of defence, carved out of the solid rock, was cut in a single night; and how the prophecy concerning a still mightier in days to come has been verified, in their simple ideas, by the great rock cuttings of

the Bhôpâl State Railway under the neighbouring mountains. Regarding this Gônd fort and its curious defences and its adjoining ruins, I may have stories to tell at another time. It is most probable that, during the existence of the Bhôjpur lake, the local climate was much affected, particularly to the east as far as Bhêlsâ. The hot winds blowing over this city must have been tempered by the mass of water to windward. The evaporation also must have been so great that the waste weir can only have had water flowing late in the rains, and only for a short while then, and therefore for some distance the water in the Bêtâ must have been during the dry season only a fraction of what it is at the present time; and floods, frequent now, must have been then of rare occurrence. This probably explains the fact that a great deal of the city of Bhêlsâ is built below the present flood level and is subject to disastrous inundations. It was possibly built when the lake existed; indeed, on conversing with the representative of one of the oldest families of Jain merchants, he assured me he had records to prove that, when his family settled in Bhêlsâ, the Bêtâ was, as he expressed it, a dry river, and, in consequence of the difficulty of procuring water in the hot season, the members of his and other families had excavated the numerous tanks and wells, the remains of which are to be found around the city. The destruction of the lake rendered their use unnecessary; and the wells were never repaired, and the tanks relapsed into fields. It is possible that the date of the total abandonment of Bêsnagar was hastened by the drying up of its principal defence and reservoir.

Before concluding, it is worth noting that the name of Dîp, a village on a small hill about half-way between Bhôpâl and the Narmadâ, and on the northern borders of the valley,—now a station on the Bhôpâl State Railway,—first attracted my attention to the traditions of the great size of the lake, which had been considered by Europeans to be much exaggerated. If the name meant anything it must mean 'island,' being a corruption of the Sanskrit *dvîpa*; and if the hill on which the village stands was an island, then the traditions only testified to what was true. The surveys I have alluded to, prove that the entire hill on which Dîp stands really was an island, perhaps two miles in length, and that the northern shore closely touched the hills which alone separated the larger lake from its storage lake—the present lake around the modern city of Bhôpâl. I am of opinion also that the name of this city is derived in the manner related by Gônd tradition; viz. Bhôj-pâl, 'the pâl or band of Râja Bhôj.'

And the reason why this *band* became to recent generations more famed than the great *pâl* near the city of Bhôjpur, is, I take it, that the Bhôpâl *pâl*, constructed exactly like the others, but immensely broad for its length and height, became a holy shrine of Buddhist temples, constructed on its broad top, which temples were all no doubt ruined when the founder of the Bhôpâl family wanted materials for the construction of the fort and walls of the citadel. The city of Bhôjpur probably rose so rapidly, from its salubrious position to importance, that it gave its name to the great lake which really was the cause of its existence.

I think there are few European visitors to these ruined sites who have not longed for a glimpse of the once beautiful lake, or a sail on its broad waters on a hot day in May over to the Buddhist ruins on Bhîmbêt, or a run up the romantic waste-weir valley, at the close of the rains, to hear the thunder of the overflow as it plunges down in broken cascades to the Bêtâ, 100 feet below, or an early morn or sunset sail among the isles and up the lovely bays on the western shore, some of them so enclosed as to appear separate lakes, surrounded by mountains nearly 1000 feet high and clothed to the water's edge by tropical verdure. Now, right through the old bed of the lake the iron rail is laid; the whistle of the engine is heard over the plain, and even penetrates the distant glens; and never again can the waters lie on the bosom of the valley which they fertilized whilst beautifying. The iron horse protects it, whilst it opens the scene I have endeavoured to portray to the western pilgrim; roads and rest-houses follow its track; and the beautiful Sâñchi tope, now renovated and restored by Government, the superb Gyârispur, Udayêsvara,—a veritable sculptured story,—the romantic Pathâri, and the picturesque Êran, all lie close to the new railway which will perhaps be, before the close of next year, the through route to convey all travellers to the north of India from Bombay.

W. KINCAID.

PROGRESS OF EUROPEAN SCHOLARSHIP.

No. XI.

Transactions of the Eastern Section of the Russian Archæological Society, Vol II., Parts 1 and 2.

(a) Meeting Feb. 9th 1887.

M. Chakhotin called the attention of Baron von Rosen to the fact that coins of the first Uthmân Amirs and other later Sultâns are on sale at Constantinople.